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Annotation: *museums are scientific, spiritual and educational treasures that deliver wealth Inherited from ancestors to the future generation. This treasure, which over the years will become rich and overflowing, will not only be a demonstration of cultural values, but also an invaluable book of speakers from the pages of a long history. Museums are a scientific, spiritual and educational treasure that supplies the wealth Inherited from ancestors to the future generation. This treasure, which over the years will become rich and overflowing, will not only be a demonstration of cultural values, but also an invaluable book of speakers from the pages of a long history.*

Museums are considered a bridge of spirituality connecting today with the past. A person of any age, whether he is a student or a representative of some field, who is visited by these masques, which embody the mysterious peculiarities of history, encourages him to realize his identity, to live with a lesson from the past. That is, in the spiritual and educational maturation of our people, the role of museums in preserving our rich heritage, studying on a scientific basis, promoting, forming feelings of national pride and pride, loyalty to the Motherland is incomparable. It is known to all of us that through the unique exhibits stored in museums, it is important to educate and strengthen the feelings of national and universal values, invaluable historical and cultural heritage, pride and pride, fatherhood and love in citizens, especially in the younger generation.

The role of museums is important in increasing the population about the history of our motherland, the path of our people's struggle for freedom. Museums serve to study our history, compare yesterday and today's life and draw the right conclusions about the progress of our society.

The independence of Uzbekistan has taken a fundamental turn in the cultural sphere, as in all aspects of economic and political life, including the study, preservation of our rich past heritage and its promotion to the broad masses of people. Among the changes and updates in the social life of our motherland, a new era also began in the activities of museums on the territory of Uzbekistan. In order to improve the activities of museums that exist on the territory of our country, to further increase their place in the spiritual moral perfection of the people, various sub-legislative acts were developed and financial funds were created.

Today, there are more than 1,200 museums in various institutions, enterprises, construction organizations, rural, community management farms, urban, district, regional centers, Jami on the territory of our country, mainly the largest of which operates in the city of Tashkent. Together with this, the house museums of dozens of writers, poets, artists, scientists and famous art figures are also functioning.

Museums are considered a cultural and educational institution, the task of which is to collect historical documents, cultural and spiritual monuments, collect and preserve samples of Natural Resources, scientifically study them and put them on exhibitions, and refer to a wide popular mass. Museums carry out cultural and educational work among the broad classes of the population. The activities of museums give great knowledge about the development of the people

in the process of historical development, their achievements and the rich cultural and spiritual heritage they left behind.

As a cultural and Educational Institution, museums are the leading means of meeting the social needs of the masses, bringing them to spiritual perfection. The establishment of new and new museums in our country, the history of the largest and most prestigious Timurid ERA in the capital, the memory of the victims of repression, the opening of the Archaeological Museum in Termez, located in the south of our country, testifies to the fact that incredibly great work is carried out by our government in the field of museum and In addition to the creation of new museums, special attention is also paid to the issue of radical improvement of the activities of all large and small museums that have been operating up to this time, reorganization in the spirit of national independence. In particular, the reopening of the Museum of the history of Uzbekistan, the equipping of the museum exposition halls on the basis of new projects and plans is a vivid evidence of our opinion. In the activities of other museums located in all regional areas, it is also felt that a step towards renewal and improvement is being made. At the present stage of socio-cultural development, it is very important to analyze the activities of museums in a general way, draw conclusions from it. The scientific analysis of the mechanism of the rise of national-spiritual values during the Muslim-Soviet regime, the occurrence of depression in the middle of the population, the further improvement of mamurian methods in the management of museums is very necessary for the cultural-manaic processes of the present day.

The culture of Uzbekistan has a rich history, closely related to the centuries-old traditions and lifestyle of the peoples of Central Asia. On the territory of Uzbekistan, located at the crossroads of the Great Silk Road, there are many architectural monuments, ancient castles and castles, mysterious and unique natural monuments and elements of folklore, most of which are now protected by UNESCO World Heritage sites. The culture of Uzbekistan has a rich history, closely related to the centuries-old traditions and lifestyle of the peoples of Central Asia. On the territory of Uzbekistan, located at the crossroads of the Great Silk Road, there are many architectural monuments, ancient castles and castles, mysterious and unique natural monuments and elements of folklore, most of which are now protected by UNESCO World Heritage sites. Today, there are 4 architectural complexes on the representative list of UNESCO World Heritage sites - the Ichan fortress Museum-Reserve in Khiva (1990), the historical center of Bukhara (1993), the historical center of Samarkand " Samarkand – crossroads of cultures " (2001), the historical center of the city, as well as Ugam-Chotqol national park (2016) and 9 intangible heritage sites. Since the independence of Uzbekistan, the country has paid great attention not only to the preservation of cultural heritage through the restoration of monuments, but also to the strengthening of national identity and recognition in World Culture. Over the millennia, the towers and ancient domes have become a beautiful reflection of the visiting card of many cities, urban landscapes, their religious and educational institutions – mosques and madrasas. In independent Uzbekistan, these unique works of ancient architects have acquired a special status as objects of invaluable cultural heritage, and they are under special protection of the state.

Of course, if the people have their own historical memory, their historical consciousness-he will inevitably deeper understand and interpret the historical-social processes that he has experienced. These attempts are embodied in the scientific activities of representatives of the people-scientists, thinkers, and are manifested by them in the scientific-theoretical analysis of society, human life and spirituality, in the creation of its known theory, principles. While museums serve as a factor in the revitalization of historical memory, the materials displayed in it are very

valuable for the culture of that time, for the message it gives from its art, as they reflect the characteristics characteristic of its time as material evidence.

In the past 7 years, mobyan implemented large-scale reforms in the field of museums in our country. Opportunities such as the free Organization of marketing services, the development of independent business plans in the creation of tourist facilities were opened to each museum. The use of audiogid devices has been established by the Bukhara State Museum Reserve in order to provide facilities for foreign tourists. Measures are being taken to consolidate the catalog of National Museums into one system by Republic. In order to improve the marketing services in museums yanda

• **As of 1 July 2022:**

- state museums are allowed to serve visitors daily until 10:00 p.m., and state museums must also set night working time periods as prescribed by legislation;
- museum employees who participate in the provision of paid services are paid additional fees and are financially encouraged, the procedure for paying additional fees and material incentives is determined by museums in agreement with their higher standing body;
- state museums were allowed to attract additional employees under a civil law contract at the expense of extra-budgetary funds, taking into account the cultural heritage agency under the Ministry of Culture and Tourism for the services organized in them, as well as the market conjuncture;
- expenses related to the organization of services by state museums were authorized to be carried out at the expense of additional sources of the local budget, extra-budgetary funds of museums, funds of the Cultural Heritage Fund, loans of commercial banks, other sources not prohibited by legislative acts;
- to attract consulting service companies with great practical experience in this direction in order to develop the field of marketing and services based on advanced foreign samples in museums;
- development of the concept and plan for the organization and development of the marketing and services sector for each museum owned by consulting service companies;
- Organization of gift (souvenir) shops, crafts workshop and outlets in museums and creation of copies of museum objects and collections-trade in souvenir products;
- ensure that state museums are guarded by National Guard personnel with funding from the state budget; (permanent from January 2023
- Organization of step-by-step “museum-restaurant” or “museum-cafes ” in museums and their territories;
- preparation of catalogs of unique objects and collections of museums, publication and establishment of their sales in bookstores;
- preparation of shows and commercials dedicated to the activities of museums in the country and the history of museum objects, as well as ensuring their display on Republican TV channels;
- practical measures such as holding historical performances and theatrical performances about our history and culture in museums and objects of cultural heritage have been applied to the field.

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